

Application of Software Engineering in Building the Portal for High-Precision Atomic Data and Computation

Parinaz Barakhshan

*Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Delaware
Newark, DE, USA
parinazb@udel.edu*

Rudolf Eigenmann

*Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Delaware
Newark, DE, USA
eigenman@udel.edu*

Bindiya Arora

*Department of Physics
Guru Nanak Dev University
India
bindiya.phy@gndu.ac.in*

Marianna S. Safronova

*Department of Physics and Astronomy
University of Delaware
Newark, DE, USA
msafrono@udel.edu*

Abstract—The Atom portal [1], udel.edu/atom, provides the scientific community with easily accessible high-quality atomic data, including energies, transition matrix elements, transition rates, radiative lifetimes, branching ratios, polarizabilities, and hyperfine constants for atoms and ions. The data are calculated using a high-precision state-of-the-art linearized coupled-cluster method. All values include estimated uncertainties. Where available, experimental results are provided with references. This paper describes some of the software engineering approaches applied in the development of the portal.

Index Terms—Computational and data-intensive (CDI) research, Best practices, Best practices for project collaborations, Best practices for software development

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of accurate atomic theory is indispensable to the design and interpretation of experiments across many applications. It is often infeasible, if not impossible, to measure relevant parameters directly.

This paper reports the release of Version 2.0 of an online portal that provides high-precision atomic data derived from computationally intensive calculations performed on a growing number of atoms/ions that would be very challenging to obtain experimentally. The codes are capable of calculating an extensive range of atomic properties to answer the significant needs of atomic, plasma, and astrophysics communities.

The latest version of the portal, Version 2.0, provides the properties transition matrix elements, transition rates, radiative lifetimes, branching ratios, hyperfine constants, quadrupole moments, scalar and dynamic polarizabilities, and energies of atoms and ions, including Li, Be⁺, Na, Mg⁺, K, Ca⁺, Rb, Sr⁺, Cs, Ba⁺, Fr, and Ra⁺. Furthermore, 13 highly charged

ions have been added to this version, including Cs⁶⁺, Ba⁷⁺, Ce⁹⁺, Pr¹⁰⁺, Nd¹¹⁺, Nd¹²⁺, Nd¹³⁺, Sm¹³⁺, Sm¹⁴⁺, Sm¹⁵⁺, Eu¹⁴⁺, Cf¹⁵⁺, and Cf¹⁷⁺.

The latest version of the portal has not just added new properties and elements; it has also improved the user interface based on community feedback. The majority of web pages are generated by scripts in order to eliminate human error and repetitive work for different elements and properties, as well as to make it easy for non-experts to create pages for newly introduced elements.

The project is an interdisciplinary effort in which physicists have produced data and computer scientists have developed the portal for presenting the data. Software engineering approaches have been applied to facilitate the portal's development during this collaboration. Practices applied to the application development process have resulted in time and effort savings.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II explains how data is generated and how it is used to create the web pages. Section III discusses some of the software engineering practices being used to build the portal, followed by conclusions in Section IV.

II. DATA GENERATION, PRESENTATION & CONSUMPTION

This section explains how physicists generate data and how computer scientists turn these data into web pages. Google Analytics data is also provided to report on the number of accesses to the portal pages and the number of downloads.

A. Data Generation

Data provided by the Atom portal is based on a long history of Physics research in developing accurate models for the computation of atomic properties and corresponding computational

codes [2]–[8], using a linearized coupled-cluster, or all-order, method [2], [9].

The computational codes have been made efficient through parallel computation using OpenMP pragmas embedded in the Fortran 90 code and running on multi-core machines. Due to the high resource demand for the code runs, parallel computations are performed on compute nodes of the Darwin computational cluster [10] [11] at the University of Delaware.

These code runs calculate the broad range of atomic properties mentioned in the introduction, using a linearized coupled-cluster method. Estimated uncertainties are included in all values. An algorithm determines the uncertainties of the electric-dipole matrix elements based on the spread of the four results, size of the correlation correction, and comparison of different contributions to the matrix elements [2]. Where available, experimental results are provided with references.

B. Data Presentation

The current version of the portal provides users with pre-computed information through an interactive interface, allowing them to access and download data instantly.

Currently, the portal utilizes a static page design, with data directly embedded in HTML. In response to user requests, like selecting the electron state of an element or ion, the data that would be displayed to the user gets filtered, and pertinent data is sent back to the user. This allows static web pages to act like dynamic web pages without relying on databases and server-side technologies.

The standardization of the names and contents of the input files that the physicists provide enabled automation of the creation of the web pages. In this process, a python script reads CSV-formatted (Comma-separated Values) data files. The related web pages will then be generated, based on the naming convention of the input files.

C. Data Consumption

A Google Analytics script has been embedded on each page in order to collect data, such as the number of users, session statistics, approximate geographical location, browser type, device information, and the number of downloads and prints. Such information can be used to measure data usage. Below are some statistics that have been taken from Google Analytics.

Over 2000 users have accessed the website since it was published in April 2021. Users are connecting from 91 countries. The top ten countries that have accessed the website were the United States (36%), Germany (11%), India (10%), United Kingdom (6%), China (5%), Canada (2%), Singapore (3%), Switzerland (2%), Philippines (2%), and France (2%). The number of downloads and prints from the website has been reported as 4,200.

D. Overall Workflow

The overall process is as follows. Original data is created by the physicists in CSV format. The data is then read by Python scripts, generating the portal HTML files. These web pages

are static, with data directly embedded in HTML. Through JavaScript functions these pages filter data and display pertinent information to the user upon request. In this way, static web pages behave just like dynamic web pages. The current design does not make use of databases and server-side technologies.

III. APPLIED SOFTWARE ENGINEERING APPROACHES

This section describes the software engineering practices applied in this project. The practices are explained in general, followed by the specific use in the project and illustrating examples. The practices are a subset of those described in [12]. The authors identify two categories: (i) best practices for project collaborations and (ii) best practices for software development. For reference, we use the same titles of the practices; we also use the term Xperts for computer and data experts supporting domain scientists (physicists, in our project).

A. Diversity of Xpert Backgrounds

Software development teams often include experts with diverse backgrounds. As a result, training should be planned so that less-familiar practices can be acquired as needed [13]. This allows for better collaboration between the experts.

In the Atom project, a number of developers from different departments and backgrounds joined the development team at various points throughout the development process. To be able to contribute to the project, each participant had to undergo a learning process.

For example, to automate the creation of web pages, developers from both computer science and physics departments were added to the project for a limited time. As needed for each person's background, we gave them time to familiarize themselves with the code, gain the skills needed for making modifications, and ask questions.

B. Breadth of Xpert Skills Needed

Computational and Data-intensive (CDI) applications today incorporate a broad range of technologies, including computing paradigms, programming languages, architectures, and algorithms.

From the Atom project's requirements, we determined the technologies to be used in the project and, in turn, the required skills for the development team. We then engaged students with the necessary expertise.

C. Collaborative Assistance Between Xperts and Domain scientists

A recommended form of interaction between Xperts and domain scientists is through collaborative assistance, where Xperts work side-by-side (physically or virtually) with the domain scientists whose project they support. Throughout the joint work, the collaborators tend to pick up sufficient knowledge of each others' skills and terminology. Supporting and facilitating collaboration between the members of the project is crucial. Regularly checking the project's progress will ensure that nothing impedes its progress.

This project engaged both physicists and computer scientists in close collaboration. The collaboration involved weekly meetings to discuss the project’s progress, updating each other on what has been done, possibly revising decisions, assigning new development tasks, and discussing the next steps.

D. Overcoming the Terminology Gap Between Computer and Domain Sciences

Computer science and domain science use different jargon. This issue may complicate understanding the problem domain and project requirements since domain scientists tend to use rich vocabulary. The key to successful collaboration is keeping the vocabularies to the essentials and investing time in explaining new terms. Using many examples and frequent feedback from both sides will help bridge this gap.

At first, in this project, it was difficult to understand the domain requirements, due to terminology gaps. While many terms are familiar to domain scientists, getting a clear understanding of their exact meaning for computer scientists has proven challenging. As a result, there were numerous questions asked by both parties so as to understand the terminologies. Additionally, the development team requested that the domain scientists provide multiple examples of the functionalities they expect from the portal. We also used prototypes to arrive at the same understanding and insights.

E. Understanding the Domain Problem and Developing a Project Plan

Xperts must devote substantial time to understanding the domain problem, turning possibly vague ideas into a feasible solution approach, and developing a clear project plan. Having a clear understanding of the project requirements for each version of the project is crucial and impacts many of the decisions that should be made along the way. Any project’s requirements need to be well thought out, balanced, and clearly understood by all involved. It is important that the identified requirements are not dropped or compromised halfway through the project.

In this project, the requirements of different versions of the project were identified, documented, discussed, and sometimes prototyped to make sure they were feasible to be implemented and reflected what the team had in mind and then implemented. The implementation was subjected to multiple revisions to ensure that it not only met the physicists’ requirements but also met those of the user community. Many examples were provided by both parties to ensure that team members were all clear about the requirements. Prototyping helped team members visualize what the final pages would look like. It also helped to highlight unanticipated design or technical challenges. By giving everyone a clear vision of the project, the prototype made everyone more involved in the entire process of building the pages.

F. Prioritize Functional Requirements

While planning the project, there is always the dilemma of many desirable features but only a short project duration.

Essential features should be differentiated from desirable requirements and should be strictly prioritized. Keep in mind that requirements can change as new insights into a research project emerge, so re-assessments and re-prioritizing of the requirements are necessary.

As part of this project, there was a discussion on how users can interact with the portal. One option was to display a periodic table to the user, with elements for which data were available being active and others greyed out. We decided, however, to prioritize elements and ions for which data was ready. We began with a simpler visual design of those elements only and created pages for each of their available properties.

G. Source Code Management and Version Control

Source code management and version control systems should be used to track the application’s evolution. Source code management tools greatly facilitate collaborative software development. Such tools enable software roll-back to a previous, well-defined state and help developers start a new branch of the software. The latter can be important if two collaborators want to add their own separate feature sets.

Because we only wanted team members to have access to the repository, we used GitHub’s private repository as the version control tool.

H. Documentation

There are many advantages to well-documented applications, and we will enlist just some of those that apply specifically to our project. Well-documented programs are easier to maintain and extend. Documentation makes it easier for new developers to reuse and extend code, which is a great concern for research teams where students graduate, leave, and are replaced by new students. Furthermore, documentation substantially enhances reproducibility.

For this purpose, we published documentation for the exclusive use of the project team on GitHub Pages. Together with Github repositories of project files, GitHub pages sharing instructions for generating the web pages improved the collaboration between team members. To put it to the test and see how helpful this documentation would be to new users, we added testers from departments other than computer science to the project and asked them to follow the instructions provided in the documentation to accomplish specific tasks. Their feedback helped us improve the documentation.

I. Maintainability & Sustainability

Sustainability [14] ensures that the software will continue to be available in the future, on new platforms, meeting new needs. A requirement of this project was maintaining the portal for a long period of time without significant additional web development, even if funding were to be discontinued. Physicists want to be able to add new elements and new properties to the portal without having to extend the code.

To fulfill this requirement, the process of creating web pages had to be automated. To this end, we standardized the file naming conventions and file content formats that

were provided by the physics collaborators. A script to create templates for different properties was developed. Using these templates, HTML files were generated based on the contents of specific property files. A Python script can process and modify the files that are read in and even generate graphical representations.

The script has the ability to run on all elements and property files associated with those elements. This feature is added in case the template itself is changed, and we want all web pages created for that property to have the same look. In addition, the script allows the user to pass the name of an individual element for which the property pages should be created. This option is used to add a new element or to update a specific data file.

Creating web pages is now as simple as dragging and dropping new data files into the repository and then running the script in one of its two forms so that relevant web pages be generated.

J. User Community Engagement and Exchange

When it comes to the design of the user interface, always involve the user community. Prototypes help obtain better feedback from the user community.

Giving presentations and talks on initial versions of this portal was a way to collect feedback from the user community. Moving forward, we will hold workshops to engage the community further.

IV. CONCLUSION

The practices that have been applied to the code development process have led to considerable time and energy savings in generating and updating the Atom portal and its web pages. Maintainability and extensibility of the code have been enhanced with documentation, particularly when introducing new team members to the project. At the same time, by automating web page generation, the project has become more sustainable.

The current portal makes available data for 25 atoms and ions. Future releases will cover up to 100 atoms and ions. Additionally, future updates will include the release of atomic computation codes, allowing researchers to reproduce some of the data currently provided through the portal. While most web pages are now generated automatically, the process of adding data to the portal will be simplified further through graphical user interfaces.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the National Science Foundation under Award No. 1931339.

REFERENCES

[1] P. Barakhshan, A. Marrs, A. Bhosale, B. Arora, R. Eigenmann, and M. S. Safronova, "Portal for high-precision atomic data and computation (version 2.0)," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.udel.edu/atom>

[2] M. S. Safronova and W. R. Johnson, "All-Order Methods for Relativistic Atomic Structure Calculations," *Advances in Atomic Molecular and Optical Physics*, vol. 55, pp. 191–233, Jan. 2008.

[3] B. Arora, M. S. Safronova, and C. W. Clark, "Magic wavelengths for the np-ns transitions in alkali-metal atoms," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 76, no. 5, p. 052509, Nov. 2007.

[4] W. R. Johnson, U. I. Safronova, A. Derevianko, and M. S. Safronova, "Relativistic many-body calculation of energies, lifetimes, hyperfine constants, and polarizabilities in L7i," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 77, no. 2, p. 022510, Feb. 2008.

[5] U. I. Safronova and M. S. Safronova, "High-accuracy calculation of energies, lifetimes, hyperfine constants, multipole polarizabilities, and blackbody radiation shift in K39," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 78, no. 5, p. 052504, Nov. 2008.

[6] D. Jiang, B. Arora, and M. S. Safronova, "Electric quadrupole moments of metastable states of Ca^+ , Sr^+ , and Ba^+ ," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 78, no. 2, p. 022514, Aug. 2008.

[7] M. S. Safronova and U. I. Safronova, "Blackbody radiation shift, multipole polarizabilities, oscillator strengths, lifetimes, hyperfine constants, and excitation energies in Ca^+ ," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 83, no. 1, p. 012503, Jan. 2011.

[8] M. S. Safronova and U. I. Safronova, "Critically evaluated theoretical energies, lifetimes, hyperfine constants, and multipole polarizabilities in $\text{Rb}87$," *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 83, no. 5, p. 052508, May 2011.

[9] M. S. Safronova, *High-precision calculations of atomic properties and parity nonconservation in systems with one valence electron*. University of Notre Dame, 2001.

[10] R. Eigenmann, B. E. Bagozzi, A. Jayaraman, W. Totten, and C. H. Wu, "DARWIN- a resource for computational and data-intensive research at the university of delaware and in the delaware region," Data Science Institute [DSI], University of Delaware, Newark, DE, Tech. Rep., 2021, <https://udspace.udel.edu/handle/19716/29071>.

[11] Data Science Institute, "DARWIN (Delaware Advanced Research Workforce and Innovation Network)," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://dsi.udel.edu/core/computational-resources/darwin/>

[12] P. Barakhshan and R. Eigenmann, "Exchanging best practices and tools for supporting computational and data-intensive research, the Xpert Network," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.09373>

[13] R. Eigenmann and P. Barakhshan, "The Xpert Network, workshop on best practices and tools for computational and data-intensive research," University Of Delaware, Report P-29, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://cpb-us-w2.wpmucdn.com/sites.udel.edu/dist/6/8980/files/2019/08/ICS-workshop-report-RE4.pdf>

[14] D. S. Katz, "Defining software sustainability," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://danielskatzblog.wordpress.com/2016/09/13/defining-software-sustainability/>